

Transliteration Analysis of Autistic Written Expression: Finding the Link between the Autistic Hypotext and the Original Text

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*morning baby cry white old man lego sky soil soil zero black
white old man walk water white old man give light zero black
white old man say light day black night morning baby cry white
old man say water sky sea sunset morning baby cry*

The text above does not make any sense: no capital letter for the first letter of the first word at the beginning of a sentence, no full-stops, no commas, no prepositions, no conjunctions ... just a string of repeated words. Such writing would be marked as ungrammatical and nonsensical by most teachers. This is not an ordinary piece of writing. It has a hidden meaningful text beneath these words. I call it *hypotext*. It was written by an autistic savant writer whom I have worked with for a few years. It is important for the teachers to understand why an autistic would write this way.

The Language Issue of Autistics

It is a widely known fact that all autistics have problems with communication. “Their language (i.e., grammar, vocabulary, even the ability to define meanings of single words) may or may not be impaired. The problem lies in the way they use whatever language they do have” (Wing, 2001, p.16).

Coleman (1989) and Rutter (1985) have estimated that approximately 40% to 50% of all autistics are mute and never develop useful spoken language. These children present educators with complex communicative situations that require flexibility and creative interventions. They will not develop functional speech; instead, they may either have no speech or they may use echolalia, often in what appears to be nonsensical forms (Simpson, 2005). According to Siegel (1996), most of these autistics unable to speak will also have mental retardation and they fall on the severe end of the autism spectrum disorder. Many will use neither sign language nor other augmentative communication devices (Coleman, 1989).

Exkorn (2005) has classified autistics under three categories of qualitative impairments in communication: (1) those with no speech; (2) those with delayed speech; and (3) those with idiosyncratic or repetitive (echolalic) speech. Autistics who can speak may be unable to imitate or hold a two-way conversation. Another sign of communication impairment is being unable to engage in make-believe play, which involves non-verbal as well as verbal communication.

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However, there is a minority group of autistics, who despite having communication impairment, display an idiosyncratic ability to express through their unique writing, but not in the normal sense of writing that we know.

Communication-based Intervention for Autistics

Every child can communicate and does communicate. Unfortunately, too often autistic children are not provided an appropriate means for spoken/written communication. This leads to aberrant behavior, because behavior is the strongest form of communication (Simpson, 2005). For autistics, the augmentative and alternative communication (AAC for short) provides them an opportunity to communicate through use of aided or unaided communication devices.

The AAC is applied to a variety of interventions that are utilized to compensate for expressive communication deficits. The AAC systems consist of two main components: (1) communication devices and (2) symbol systems (McCormick & Shane, 1990). Communication devices are either aided or unaided. Unaided communication devices do not require any technology to operate. They include gestures, body language, vocalizations, and sign language (Bondy & Frost, 2002). The advantages of using unaided systems are threefold: firstly, no external support devices are necessary; secondly, they are easy to carry among environments; and lastly, there is no cost involved (Simpson, 2005). Aided communication devices require technology that is external to the child. These include computers and speech output devices. The two main advantages of using aided systems are the ability of the user to produce complex messages and to communicate at a distance (Kuder, 1997).

Symbol systems utilized in AAC take many forms. One of the most common types of symbol systems is manual sign, which includes sign languages (e.g., American Sign Language and Australian Sign Language) and Sign Exact English. Sign language has been used effectively with many disabilities, including autism (Bryen & Joyce, 1986). Additional types of symbols typically used for AAC devices include abstract symbol-systems such as, Picture Communication Symbols (Johnson, 1981), Picsyms (Carlson, 1984), Sigsymbols (Creagan, 1982), Picture Exchange Communication System (Frost & Bondy, 1994), and Boardmaker (Mayer-Johnson Inc., 2001).

Whichever AAC system an autistic uses, it serves as a hyperlink between the intrinsic world of the autistic and his/her extrinsic world of the immediate surrounding that consists of both animate beings and inanimate objects. How the autistic learns is still not fully understood yet, but self-stimulatory behavior (also known as “stimming”), which many autistics often engage (e.g., vocalizing in the form of humming, tapping surfaces with fingers, and sniffing objects), seems to play an initial role in the mechanical processing intake of sensory perceptual information such as hearing, seeing and motor movements (Sticht, Beck, Hauke, Kleiman, & James, 1974) but apparently fails to make any meaningful connection with the information processing of the information input (i.e., listening, looking and writing) which is essential to making sense of whatever that is being communicated. To succeed in establishing meaningful contact with the environment, the autistic must have an intact cognitive capacity operating at birth for the purpose of storing, retrieving and using information. Without this important basic adaptive process, no meaningful learning could take place.

A Case Study of an Autistic Writer

In this article, I shall discuss one 12-year-old autistic writer (see Chia, 2007). Let me call him JJ, who belongs to Exkorn's (2005) third category of communication impairment. I worked with JJ a few years ago. He could read very well but could not understand. Such a condition is described as hyperlexic.

JJ rarely talks but he is an avid reader. What differentiates JJ from other children his age is that he virtually never reads stories with elaborate plots and highly-developed characters. JJ reads fact-filled material only. Left on his own, JJ is more than happy to read the same book about outer space or countries he has visited, for instance, over and over.

JJ spends more time writing than reading. His parents describe him as an obsessive writer, and JJ has written several books of "stories" but nobody could really understand after reading them. JJ's strong preference to read or write is not surprising. According to Siegel (1996), autistics express themselves better in writing than in spoken language. One reason for this may be that "the expressive language problems associated with autism may be partly related to the speed with which processing of spoken language should occur. ... The second probable explanation for why many higher functioning autistic people write better than they speak is that speaking is a more social activity than writing. All the language pragmatics and social interactional aspects of a conversation – which present enormous difficulties in autism – impinge upon the thinking of an autistic when he speaks. When he writes, he can be alone" (Siegel, 1996, p.279). Therefore, writing can be a good modality for encouraging expression in autistics.

Autistic Written Expression: Finding the Hidden Hyperlinks

Some time, three years ago, I spent almost a week with JJ at his home, interviewing his parents, watching him doing anything alone, poring through several photograph albums of JJ and his family visiting different cities all over the world and participating in various exciting activities. I painstakingly tried to make sense of what JJ had written. Each word/phrase could be linked up to an event/episode that had happened or anything that was taking place in JJ's life.

Returning to the excerpt shown at the beginning, I asked myself, "What is JJ trying to tell me?" Could there be some kind of underlying meanings? In my first attempt to analyze the excerpt, I tried to cut the endless string of words into single words, phrases and/or clauses to make sense. For instance, the word "morning" refers to time of the day (a *time antecedent*), while "baby cry" refers to an incident that has happened at home, that is, JJ's baby brother cried cry for milk (an *episodic antecedent*). My only problem with the word and the phrase is: so what do they mean? What was JJ trying to tell me?

The next phrase "white old man" kept me pondering who JJ was referring to. I had to find out from JJ's parents through probing questions and soon learnt that JJ once visited the Vatican City on a family tour. They saw the beautiful painting done by Michaelangelo of a white bearded man (representing God) stretching his arm to touch the finger of a mortal man (representing Adam) on the ceiling of a cathedral. They showed me the photographs taken at the cathedral. On one photograph, I saw JJ being held up by his father and his eyes seemed to fix on the Michaelangelo

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painting on the ceiling. “Eureka!” I exclaimed excitedly. “That ‘white old man’ refers to God.” The photographs are *pictorial antecedents*.

The word “lego” refers to a construction set of plastic bricks that JJ’s father had bought him as a birthday present. The word could mean “to make” something that JJ associated with. JJ could use the Lego bricks to make anything he liked, say a house or a horse. JJ probably used the concrete word “lego” as an action word (verb). In this case, “lego” is an *activity-related object antecedent*. The last two words “sky” and “soil” are something physical that JJ could identify. From my conversation with JJ’s parents, I discovered that his mother would read the Bible to him every evening at the balcony of their flat. She used concrete examples to make sense of the verses to JJ. The word “sky” (JJ would point upward when asked, “What’s sky?”) was used to substitute “heavens”; the word “soil” (JJ would point downward when asked, “What’s soil?”), “earth”. It began to make more sense to me than before. The “sky” and “soil” are what I called *non-activity-related object antecedents*. Confidently, I stringed all these transliterated words together to form the following sentence: “Beginning of the day an incident God to make heavens earth.” This sentence looks very familiar. It is very much like the first verse found in the first biblical book of Genesis. What JJ had done was conscientiously re-phrasing the biblical verse that he had heard/read before in the way he could best understand by associating them with the happenings and physical objects around him. In brief, the autistic hypotext – “morning baby cry white old man lego sky soil” – means “In the beginning God created heavens and earth” (Genesis 1:1) in its original text. Figure 1 shows the painting done by Michelangelo of God creating the first human - a man - and named him Adam.

Figure 1. Michelangelo’s Painting of God creating Adam the First Man

What I have done here is to show that the words/phrases JJ used in his writing are related to some kinds of antecedents. They do not happen meaninglessly. JJ understood them and it is up to me to find out what they mean. In order to decipher the meaning out of the apparently meaningless string of words, I have to understand the incidents experienced by JJ and the objects he has seen/handed before. They are the hidden antecedents of the words/phrases in his writing.

Transliteration Analysis: Understanding the Autistic Writing Process

It is interesting to note that JJ could read the entire verse of Genesis 1:1 (original text) without any problem, no omission or change of words. However, when he was asked to write the verse, he expressed it in his own writing style (see Figure 1). He wrote his unique hypotext for his class composition: “My Favorite Book.”

Figure 2. The Transliteration of JJ's Sentence (Hypotext) from the Original Text

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In his own written expression, all the words put together somewhat seemed to make sense to him but not to me. This is dissociative processing. Corsini (2002) describes it as an unconscious process in which one or more parts of mental functioning become split off from others and appear to operate outside of consciousness. Hence, in JJ's case, the words/phrases – morning, baby cry, white old man, lego, sky, soil – do not link coherently together. The sentence appears nonsensical and is certainly ungrammatical. The words/phrases are dissociated from one another. However, JJ was able to link each word/phrase to a past/current incident (e.g., a visit to a cathedral in the Vatican City) or something encountered on a regular basis in the past (e.g., his baby brother cried for milk every morning three years ago) as well as objects (e.g., Lego bricks) that he had seen and/or handled before. Such incidents and objects have provided associative meanings to JJ and so as to enable him to express himself in his own unique written language. At the same time, each of his word/phrase is also associated with the word/s found in the original text he had heard/read before. This is associative processing, which “occurs as a result of life experiences based on connections made to personal, historical events” (Corsini, 2002, p.71). It is observed that JJ often omitted functional words (e.g., articles and conjunctions) which are meaningless to him.

The less obvious parallel processing also takes place between JJ's own idiosyncratic hypotext and the original text of the verse simultaneously during the dissociative and associative processes of writing. Corsini (2002) describes parallel processing as that information processing of two separate but related sets of information sources that “are attended to simultaneously, thus accounting for the apparent ability to carry on different cognitive functions at the same time. One information source may be processed consciously (i.e., JJ's own hypotext) whereas another source (i.e., the original verse) is attended subconsciously” (p.690).

With this interpretation of JJ's written expression of his thoughts, I was at first skeptical of JJ's ability to construct his hypotextual sentences. I went on to do several more transliteration analyses of other sentences found in his other exercise books. It was tedious, but rewarding, especially when these once ungrammatical, nonsensical sentences now become meaningful to me.

Conclusion

I repeated the experiment with three other autistic writers. The transliteration analysis did work successfully with two but I did not manage to break into the third one. More evidence-based research studies on transliteration analysis as an ACC system should be done in future with two goals in mind: (1) finding hyperlinks that can help to make sense of an autistic hypotext, and (2) breaking the myth surrounding autism as well as opening the once silent, often misunderstood, world of the autistics through their unique, perhaps even creative, writing style.

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